

Studies on Metal Ammine Complexes—Part II. Polarographic Behaviour of Some Schiff Base Pentaammine Chromium(III) Complexes

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The polarographic behaviour of several newly synthesised chromium(III) complexes with Schiff bases has been described. The reduction waves in 0.1M LiCl corresponded to one electron reduction. These are diffusion controlled and irreversible in nature. The values of $k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ lie between 10^{-9} to 10^{-11} cm²s⁻¹. The irreversible behaviour may be interpreted in terms of 'Loosening' of the chromium(III) complex during reduction from Cr(III) to Cr(II). The complexes have been characterised by chemical analysis, conductance measurements and infrared spectra.

THE Schiff bases derived from amino acids are known to play an important role in biological reactions¹.

With an aim to elucidate the role of such Schiff bases as electron mediators, our previous studies²⁻⁴ have now been extended to the complexes of the Schiff bases with pentaammine chromium(III) to gain further information on the problem. The results on the reduction of these complexes at the d.m.e. are presented in this communication.

Experimental

All reagents were AnalaR grade BDH products and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The organic solvents and salicylaldehyde were laboratory grade reagents. They were distilled twice prior to use.

Monochloropentaammine chromium(III) chloride was prepared by the method given Schlessinger⁵. The crude product was recrystallised from water and its spectra agreed with the literature values⁶.

Two series of Schiff bases: (i) derived from amino acids and (ii) derived from aminobenzoic acids were used. The Schiff bases of amino acids were prepared by the method of Dietrich as adopted by Martell⁷ by condensing glycine(Gly), alanine(Ala), aspartic acid (S-A) and glutamic acid (G) with salicylaldehyde(S) and *o*-vanillin(V). The Schiff bases of amino benzoic acids were prepared by the method of Roe and Montgomery⁸ by condensing *o*-aminobenzoic acid (OAB), *m*-aminobenzoic acid (MAB) and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (PAB) with benzaldehyde (B), salicylaldehyde(S) and *o*-vanillin(V).

Preparation of the Complexes :

Complexes with Schiff bases derived from amino acids were prepared by warming to 50° for 30 min a solution containing 0.02 mole of the Schiff base and

0.01 mole of chloropentaammine chromium(III) chloride in 100 ml of water. After cooling to below 5°, 10 ml of 70% HClO₄ was added and the crude product washed first with alcohol and then with ether till free from HClO₄. After suspending in 100 ml of methanol, the product was stirred magnetically for 15 min and filtered off. The methanolic filtrate was concentrated to about 10 ml under vacuum at 40° and then cooled to below 5°. The desired complex was precipitated by adding 1:1 alcohol-ether mixture and recrystallised from 1M HClO₄ by adding ice cold 70% HClO₄. The pink product was washed thoroughly with alcohol till free from HClO₄ and then with ether and dried under vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Complexes of Schiff bases derived from amino benzoic acids were prepared by adding 0.1 mole of the Schiff base to 100 ml of a solution containing 2.4 g of chloropentaammine chromium(III) chloride and adjusting the pH to between 4-5 with Li₂CO₃. After heating at 50° for 30 min with magnetic stirring, the solution was cooled to room temperature and the insoluble material filtered off. The filtrate was cooled to about 2° in an ice bath and the complex precipitated by adding 10 ml of ice cold saturated NaClO₄. After standing in ice bath for 15 min, the precipitate was filtered off and washed with alcohol. The crude product was magnetically stirred for 30 min with 100 ml of methanol and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under vacuum to about 10 ml and the desired complex precipitated by cooling in ice and adding ether. It was then recrystallised from 1M HClO₄ by adding 70% ice cold HClO₄, washed with alcohol, ether and dried under vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. The complexes with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids were also prepared by the above method.

The complexes were subjected to chemical analysis for chromium, nitrogen and carbon. The complex was decomposed by prolonged heating with a strong

solution of NaOH and chromium estimated spectrophotometrically as chromate⁹ after treating with hydrogen peroxide. These results were cross checked by estimating chromium with diphenyl carbazide¹⁰ at 540 nm. Nitrogen and carbon were estimated at the Microanalytical Laboratories, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow (Table 1).

The molar conductance of the complexes was measured with a Systronics Conductivity Meter, Type

302, at 25 ± 0.1° using a dip type cell. The conductance was measured with a 1.0 × 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes. The absorption spectra was recorded on a Carl-Zeiss, Specord, recording spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra was recorded on Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer in KBr by thin film technique.

Polarograms were recorded on a Cambridge pen recording polarograph using a d.m.e. and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. The capillary

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE, VISIBLE AND INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF THE SCHIFF BASE SUBSTITUTED CHROMIUM(III) PENTAAMMINE COMPLEXES

Complex R=[Cr(NH ₃) ₅]	Chemical Analysis						Molar conductance at 25 ± .1°C ohm ⁻¹ cm ²	Wave-length of max. absorption λ _{max} ± 1nm	Infrared absorption band at cm ⁻¹		
	Chromium %		Nitrogen %		Carbon %				(COO ⁻) _{asy} and NH ₃ defor.	(COO ⁻) _{sym}	(C=N)
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.			10	11	12
[R-S-Gly](ClO ₄) ₂	10.00	10.11	16.40	16.34	23.45	23.34	260	525	1610	1415	1640
[R-S-Ala](ClO ₄) ₂	9.90	9.84	15.82	15.92	25.12	25.00	260	522	1610	1410	1650
[R-S-A](ClO ₄) ₂	9.15	9.09	14.70	14.66	25.02	25.17	255	522	1600	1410	1640
[R-S-G](ClO ₄) ₂	8.82	8.87	14.27	14.33	26.75	26.67	250	520	1600	1405	1640
[R-V-Gly](ClO ₄) ₂	9.62	9.55	15.49	15.44	24.21	24.26	255	527	1605	1410	1640
[R-V-Ala](ClO ₄) ₂	9.27	9.31	15.13	15.03	25.96	25.80	250	525	1610	1410	1650
[R-V-A](ClO ₄) ₂	8.52	8.63	13.82	13.95	25.78	25.91	245	524	1610	1410	1650
[R-V-G](ClO ₄) ₂	8.51	8.44	13.55	13.63	27.17	27.27	245	528	1610	1400	1640
[R-OAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.00	9.08	14.50	14.67	14.80	14.67	350	517	1610	1400	—
[R-B-OAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.22	9.28	14.90	15.00	30.08	30.00	245	520	1610	1390	1650
[R-S-OAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.10	9.02	14.65	14.58	29.01	29.16	245	522	1605	1400	1640
[R-V-OAB](ClO ₄) ₂	8.64	8.58	13.92	13.87	29.60	29.70	240	522	1600	1400	1640
[R-MAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.20	9.08	14.55	14.67	14.50	14.67	340	521	1605	1380	—
[R-B-MAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.22	9.28	15.08	15.00	30.07	30.00	245	522	1605	1380	1650
[R-S-MAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.06	9.02	14.52	14.58	29.25	29.16	250	525	1605	1380	1640
[R-V-MAB](ClO ₄) ₂	8.52	8.58	13.82	13.87	29.65	29.70	245	525	1605	1400	1650
[R-PAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.15	9.08	14.55	14.67	14.78	14.67	345	520	1600	1385	—
[R-B-PAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.20	9.28	15.06	15.00	29.95	30.00	240	521	1610	1380	1640
[R-S-PAB](ClO ₄) ₂	9.10	9.02	14.53	14.58	29.25	29.16	235	522	1605	1385	1640
[R-V-PAB](ClO ₄) ₂	8.50	8.58	13.80	13.87	29.80	29.70	235	522	1600	1400	1640

characteristic $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ was found to be $1.77 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ S}^{-1/2}$. The temperature was maintained constant at 25° with a water thermostat. The polarograms were always recorded using freshly prepared solutions of the complexes in perchloric acid maintaining the pH at 3.0. The solutions were prepared by taking 1.0 to 7.0 ml solution of the complex (conc. about $0.01M$) and adding to them 0.4 ml of 0.1% gelatin and 1.0 ml of $1M$ LiCl. The total volume was made upto 10 ml in each case with perchloric acid of pH 3.0.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analysis (Table 1) of the complexes confirms the formulae $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{SB}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{AB}](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ where SB and AB represent the Schiff base and (*o*-, *m*- or *p*-) aminobenzoic acid respectively. Molar conductance values (Table 1) of the complexes lie in the range 235-260 and 340-350 respectively. The complexes gave λ_{max} in the range 517-530 nm.

The infrared spectra of the Schiff base pentaammine chromium(III) complexes show two bands around 1400 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} (Table 1) which may be assigned to the symmetric and the asymmetric stretching of the carboxylic group^{11,12}. In the case of complexes of the dicarboxylic acids (aspartic acid and glutamic acid), an additional band around 1700 cm^{-1} is observed which may be assigned to a free carboxyl group, indicating that in these complexes only one carboxyl group is involved in coordination. It is also observed that nitrogen of the C=N group of the Schiff base is not involved in complex formation since the band around $1640\text{-}1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ present in the spectra of Schiff bases due to the C=N group does not show any shift. The complexes may then be represented as $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{OOCR}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$.

In order to choose an appropriate supporting electrolyte, polarograms of the complexes were recorded using a number of supporting electrolytes. It was observed that well defined waves were obtained with $0.1M$ LiCl and $0.1M$ NaClO₄ as supporting electrolyte. The present studies were carried out in $0.1M$ LiCl. The complexes were found to undergo irreversible reduction. This is evident from the fact that the slope of the plots between $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ and E gave fractional values of *n* (of the order of 0.5) and $E_{1/2}$ show a shift with a change in concentration of the complex. The values of $i_d/h^{1/2}$ are constant indicating a diffusion controlled electrode process.

The diffusion coefficient, *D*, was evaluated with the help of Nernst Equation¹³ :

$$D = \frac{RT}{ZF^2} \lambda_\alpha \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

where *Z* is the charge on the ion and λ_α is the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution. The ionic conductance of complex ion $[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{SB}]^{++}$ or

$[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{AB}]^{+++}$ was calculated by subtracting the conductance value of the perchlorate ion ($71 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 25°) from the total conductance given in Table 1. The value obtained from this equation gives an approximate value of *D* because the molar conductance value used is for $0.01M$ solution rather than at infinite dilution. This approximate value of *D* when substituted in the Ilkovic equation enables one to calculate the value of *n*, the number of electrons involved in the electrode reaction. The values of *n* were calculated to be Ca 1.0, indicating a one electron transfer electrode process. The exact values of *D* (Table 2) were then evaluated from the Ilkovic equation using a value of *n*=1. Finally the values of *D* were used

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA AT 25°C IN $0.1M$ LITHIUM CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF 0.004% GELATIN FOR THE SCHIFF BASE SUBSTITUTED PENTAAMMINE CHROMIUM(III) PERCHLORATES.

Chromium(III) pentaammine complex with	$-E_{1/2} \text{ V}$ (vs SCE)	αn	$D^{1/2} \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$K_{f,h}^0 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$
1	2	3	4	5
S-Gly	0.87	0.64	4.09	5.42
S-Ala	0.91	0.62	5.16	2.31
S-A	0.90	0.65	5.23	1.97
S-G	0.90	0.63	5.38	1.84
V-Gly	0.89	0.67	4.87	0.74
V-Ala	0.91	0.63	4.77	1.63
V-A	0.88	0.63	5.38	3.40
V-G	0.92	0.59	5.39	7.62
OAB	0.98	0.63	4.27	2.81
B-OAB	0.91	0.67	4.75	6.76
S-OAB	0.94	0.60	4.26	19.40
V-OAB	0.93	0.60	5.10	38.90
MAB	0.91	0.77	4.95	0.373
B-MAB	0.91	0.81	4.55	0.088
S-MAB	0.90	0.77	4.87	0.495
V-MAB	0.88	0.82	4.32	0.450
PAB	0.90	0.72	5.17	2.47
B-PAB	0.89	0.78	4.32	0.485
S-PAB	0.90	0.81	4.64	0.288
V-PAB	0.90	0.77	4.74	1.09

to calculate $K_{f,h}^0$, the formal rate constant for the electrode reaction, using the equation for an irreversible process¹³⁻¹⁵.

$$E_{d,s} + 0.2412 = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^0}{D^{1/2}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \left[\log \frac{i}{i_a - i} - 0.546 \log t \right]$$

A plot of $E_{d,s}$ versus $\left[\log \frac{i}{i_a - i} - 0.546 \log t \right]$ gives a slope equal to $\frac{0.0542}{\alpha n}$ and intercept equal to $\frac{0.05915}{\alpha n}$

$$\log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^0}{D^{1/2}} - 0.2412.$$

The values of $K_{f,h}^0$ (Table 2) lie in the range of 10^{-9} to $10^{-11} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ which further confirm the irreversible behaviour of the reduction waves. Since the reduction is a one electron transfer process the observed irreversible wave corresponds to the reduction of Cr(III) to Cr(II) and may be expressed as :

The irreversibility of the reduction step may be attributed to the change of configuration from $3d^3 4s 4p^3$ to $4s 4p^3 4d^2$. The 'loosening' of chromium(III) complex during the course of the reduction is in accord with the low rate of the electrode process. The $4s 4p^3 4d^2$ configuration for the Cr(II) complex has been demonstrated^{16,17} for a Cr(II)-ethylene diamine complex which shows a magnetic moment of 4.4-4.5 B.M.

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